

THE FILIPINOS' ENDURING HOPE: A STUDY ON LOSS OF EMPLOYMENT AND LOSS OF A LOVED ONE DURING THE PANDEMIC AS FACTORS IN THE HOPE SCALE SCORES OF SELECTED COLLEGE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study attempted to establish the effect of loss of employment of a family member and loss of life of a family member or relative as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic on Hope Scale Scores of the respondents. The respondents of this study were college students of a local government college in the Province of Rizal, Philippines and were purposively chosen for comparative analysis. The results reveal that the mean scores of the respondents whose family member did not lose employment as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic and those of the respondents whose family member or relative did not die as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic were consistently higher in Pathway, Agency and Total Hope Scale Scores. However, these differences were not found to be significant.

I. INTRODUCTION

During the first year of the COVID-19 pandemic, 4.5 million Filipinos lost their jobs.¹ Fortunately, the unemployment rate of the country has been steadily going down and has recently been reported to be at 5.2% as of July of 2022.² Since the beginning of COVID-19, an estimated 62,000 or so Filipinos also lost their lives.³

Not only have there been loss of employment and life, the government lockdowns during the first few months of the pandemic have caused social isolation, which have worsened the mental health challenges of many Filipinos.⁴ The general fear and uncertainty have impacted mental health in the country, which have increased the people's stress and rates of depression.⁵

One factor that has been shown to mitigate mental health challenges is hope, which has been linked to improved coping, better well-being, is found to be a moderator between depression and negative life events and also as a protective factor in suicide.⁶

Individuals with high hope are expected to view stressful situations as challenging rather than threatening, thereby decreasing the intensity of stress and prevents its proliferation.⁷ Hope has been found to be a motivational factor that helps facilitate and sustain achievement of long-term goals, including the flexible management of difficulties that become obstacles in goal attainment.⁸ With its natural orientation towards the future, hope motivates individuals to preserve their positive involvement in life irrespective of any limitations.⁹

Hope is significantly associated with superior academic and athletic performance, better physical and psychological wellbeing, enhanced self-esteem, and improved interpersonal relationships.¹⁰ Hope can be seen as a protective factor against the development of chronic anxiety.¹¹ It has also been shown to possess the potential to enhance wellbeing over time,¹² and is positively associated with overall life satisfaction.¹³

Snyder et al (1991), developed an instrument to measure hope, which consists of 12 items and is divided into the domains of Agency, or goal-directed energy and Pathways, or planning to accomplish goals.¹⁴ There are 4 items for each domain and the remainder are fillers. The items use an 8-point Likert scale.

Using this instrument, this study attempted to ascertain the impact of the occurrence or non-occurrence of loss of employment of a family member as well as the occurrence or non-occurrence of loss of life of a family member or relative as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic on the hope scale scores of the respondents.

In particular, this study sought to address the following research questions:

1. What are the Agency, Pathways and Total Hope Scale Scores of
 - 1.1 respondents whose family member lost employment as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic;
 - 1.2 respondents whose family members did not lose employment as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic?
2. What are the Agency, Pathways and Total Hope Scale Scores of

- 2.1 respondents whose family member or relative died as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic;
- 2.2 respondents whose family members or relative did not die as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic?
- 3. Are there significant differences in the Agency, Pathways and Total Hope Scale Scores
 - 3.1 between respondents whose family member lost employment and respondents whose family member did not lose employment as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic;
 - 3.2 between respondents whose family member or relative died and respondents whose family member or relative did not die as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic?

II. METHODOLOGY

In selecting the respondents, the population of 3rd year college students of a particular local government college in the Province of Rizal, Philippines was chosen. For research question number 1, purposive quota sampling was employed. 42 college students whose family member lost employment as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic and 42 college students whose family member did not lose employment as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic were obtained. For research question number 2, purposive quota sampling was also utilized. 49 college students whose family member or relative died as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic and 49 college students whose family member or relative did not die as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic were obtained.

The instrument used was the Adult Hope Scale developed by Snyder et al (1991).¹⁴ A Google forms online version of the instrument was created and was administered anonymously on the respondents who all volunteered for this study. Table 1 shows the items of the instrument, while Table 2 presents the points assigned in the scoring.

Table 1: Hope Scale Items

Item	Subscale measured
1. I can think of many ways to get out of a jam.	Pathway
2. I energetically pursue my goals.	Agency
3. I feel tired most of the time.	Filler
4. There are lots of ways around any problem.	Pathway
5. I am easily downed in an argument.	Filler
6. I can think of many ways to get the things in life that are important to me.	Pathway
7. I worry about my health.	Filler
8. Even when others get discouraged, I know I can find a way to solve the problem.	Pathway
9. My past experiences have prepared me well for my future.	Agency
10. I've been pretty successful in life.	Agency
11. I usually find myself worrying about something.	Filler
12. I meet the goals that I set for myself.	Agency

Table 2: Hope Scale Item Responses

Response	Equivalent Points
Definitely False	1
Mostly False	2
Somewhat False	3
Slightly False	4
Slightly True	5
Somewhat True	6
Mostly True	7
Definitely True	8

III. RESULTS

The following tables present the data gathered for this study including the profile of the respondents as well as the statistical calculations necessary to answer the research questions.

Table 3: Profile of Respondents
Loss of Employment of Family Member

	Males	Females	Mean Age
Yes	7	35	21.80952
No	8	34	21.16667
	15	69	21.488095

Table 4: Loss of Employment of Family Member
Hope Scale: Pathway Scores

Group	Yes	No
Mean	25.79	26.48
SD	4.04	2.86
SEM	0.62	0.44
N	42	42
<p>P value and statistical significance: The two-tailed P value equals 0.3689 By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be not statistically significant. Confidence interval: The mean of Yes minus No equals -0.69 95% confidence interval of this difference: From -2.21 to 0.83 Intermediate values used in calculations: t = 0.9036 df = 82 standard error of difference = 0.764</p>		

Table 5: Loss of Employment of Family Member
Hope Scale: Agency Scores

Group	Yes	No
Mean	24.07	24.62
SD	5.01	3.77
SEM	0.77	0.58
N	42	42
<p>P value and statistical significance: The two-tailed P value equals 0.5730 By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be not statistically significant. Confidence interval:</p>		

The mean of Yes minus No equals -0.55
 95% confidence interval of this difference: From -2.47 to 1.38
 Intermediate values used in calculations:
 $t = 0.5659$
 $df = 82$
 standard error of difference = 0.968

Table 6: Loss of Employment of Family Member
 Total Hope Scale Scores (Pathway + Agency)

Group	Yes	No
Mean	49.86	51.1
SD	8.15	5.74
SEM	1.26	0.89
N	42	42

P value and statistical significance:
 The two-tailed P value equals 0.4233
 By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be **not statistically significant.**
 Confidence interval:
 The mean of Yes minus No equals -1.24
 95% confidence interval of this difference: From -4.30 to 1.82
 Intermediate values used in calculations:
 $t = 0.8047$
 $df = 82$
 standard error of difference = 1.539

Table 7: Loss of Family Member or Relative
 Profile of Respondents

	Males	Females	Mean Age
Yes	11	38	21.26531
No	13	36	21.55102
Total	24	74	21.408165

Table 8: Loss of Family Member or Relative
 Hope Scale: Pathway Scores

Group	Yes	No
Mean	25.29	26.14
SD	4.17	3.83
SEM	0.6	0.55
N	49	49

P value and statistical significance:
 The two-tailed P value equals 0.2921

By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be **not statistically significant.**
 Confidence interval:
 The mean of Yes minus No equals -0.86
 95% confidence interval of this difference: From -2.46 to 0.75
 Intermediate values used in calculations:
 $t = 1.0593$
 $df = 96$
 standard error of difference = 0.809

Table 9: Loss of Family Member or Relative
 Hope Scale: Agency Scores

Group	Yes	No
Mean	24.39	24.45
SD	4.78	3.94
SEM	0.68	0.56
N	49	49

P value and statistical significance:
 The two-tailed P value equals 0.9450
 By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be **not statistically significant.**
 Confidence interval:
 The mean of Yes minus No equals -0.06
 95% confidence interval of this difference: From -1.82 to 1.70
 Intermediate values used in calculations:
 $t = 0.0692$
 $df = 96$
 standard error of difference = 0.885

Table 10: Loss of Family Member or Relative
 Total Hope Scale Scores
 (Pathway + Agency)

Group	Yes	No
Mean	49.67	50.59
SD	8.46	6.23
SEM	1.21	0.89
N	49	49

P value and statistical significance:
 The two-tailed P value equals 0.5422
 By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be **not statistically significant.**
 Confidence interval:

The mean of Yes minus No equals -0.92
95% confidence interval of this difference: From -3.90 to 2.06
Intermediate values used in calculations:
 $t = 0.6117$
 $df = 96$
standard error of difference = 1.501

IV. CONCLUSION

Of the 42 college students whose family member lost employment as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, 7 were male while 35 were female. Of the 42 college students whose family member did not lose employment as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, 8 were male and 34 were female. The mean age for all 84 respondents was 21.49.

The Hope Scale Pathway mean score of the respondents whose family member lost employment as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic was 25.79 while the Hope Scale Pathway mean score of the respondents whose family member did not lose employment as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic was 26.48, which is higher. However, upon computing the unpaired t test, this difference was not statistically significant.

The Hope Scale Agency mean score of the respondents whose family member lost employment of the COVID-19 pandemic was 24.07 while the Hope Scale Agency mean score of the respondents whose family member did lose employment as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic was 24.62, which is higher. However, upon computing the unpaired t test, this difference was also not statistically significant.

The Total Hope Scale (Pathway + Agency) mean score of the respondents whose family member lost employment as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic was 49.86 while the Total Hope Scale (Pathway + Agency) mean score of the respondents whose family member did not lose employment as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic was 51.1, which is higher. However, upon computing the unpaired t test, this difference was once again not statistically significant.

Of the 49 college students whose family member or relative died as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, 11 were male and 38 were female. And of the 49 college students whose family member or relative did not die as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, 13 were male and 36 were female. The mean age for all 98 respondents was 21.40.

The Hope Scale Pathway mean score of the whose family member or relative died as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic was 25.29 while the Hope Scale Pathway mean score of the respondents whose family member or relative did not die as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic was 26.14, which is higher. However, upon computing the unpaired t test, this difference was not statistically significant.

The Hope Scale Agency mean score of the respondents whose family member or relative died as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic was 24.39 while the Hope Scale Agency mean score of the respondents whose family member or relative did not die as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic was 24.45, which is higher. However, upon computing the unpaired t test, this difference was also not statistically significant.

The Total Hope Scale (Pathway + Agency) mean score of the respondents whose family member or relative died as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic was 49.67 while the Total Hope Scale (Pathway + Agency) mean score of the respondents whose family member or relative did not die as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic was 50.59, which is higher. However, upon computing the unpaired t test, this difference was once again not statistically significant.

Although the mean scores of the respondents whose family member did not lose employment as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic and those of the respondents whose family member or relative did not die as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic are consistently higher in Pathway, Agency and Total Hope Scale Scores, these differences were not found to be significant.

These results could be explained in part by the findings of an SWS survey which reported that 93% of Filipinos were optimistic for 2022 with the National Capital Region as having the highest recorded hope at 95%.¹⁵

Further research is recommended concerning the almost negligible impact of loss of employment of a family member and loss of a relative or family member during the COVID-19 pandemic, which could reveal some yet unexplored character trait of Filipinos that is their source of hope.

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